

THE IMPORTANCE OF DANCE, ITS EFFECT ON HEALTH

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Annotation: In this article, the unique features of the art of dance. Information is given about the views of scholars and thinkers that the attractive behavior and situations of dance have a great impact on human health.

Key words: dance, pleasure, health, healing dance, dance-movement therapy.

Introduction.

Today, as there is development in every field, many changes and reforms are being implemented in the fields of culture and art. Special attention was paid to the national dance art by our honorable President, measures and regulatory documents were adopted for the representatives of this field to increase their scientific potential and to continue the traditions of national dance and to develop the field of art. Including DP-4584 adopted on February 4, 2020 "On measures for the further development of national dance art" and DP-4585 adopted on February 4, 2020 "Raks san" Our decision on measures to fundamentally improve the system of training highly qualified personnel in the field of science and to further develop its scientific potential"[4] is a clear proof of our opinion.

The Uzbek people have always been an artistic people, that's why holidays, wedding performances are celebrated with all kinds of joyful days, songs and dances. Today, the rich music and dance art of the Uzbek people is in the center of everyone's attention. In particular, efforts are being made at the state level to raise the level of art "Maqom" and "lazgi" to the highest level today. Preserving the intangible heritage of our art and delivering it to the future generation in its original form is one of the most important issues.

On December 12, 2019, "Lazgi" was included in the representative list of the intangible heritage of humanity as an element of the cultural heritage of Uzbekistan. It is worth noting that Khorezm "Lazgi" was included in the representative list of the Intangible Heritage of Humanity by the Intergovernmental Committee for the Protection of the Intangible Heritage of UNESCO.

The appearance of the "Lazgi" dance has its own legendary history, that is, "The human body was originally made of clay and was separate. They tell the soul to "enter the body", the soul enters the body and suddenly comes back out

in fear. "Enter the body," they ordered again. He said: "I'm afraid." Then a melody was heard in the hymn. Enchanted by this melody, the soul did not know how it entered the body. First, life entered his fingers, paws, wrists, and shoulders, and a person was resurrected. It was the divine "Lazgi" tune. There are hundreds of truths behind every myth.

The emergence of the Uzbek national dance (lazgi) art and its attractive movements, quiet colors, and unique melodies are fundamentally different from other types of art. A meaning and content is hidden in every movement of a dancer, and its correct delivery to the audience requires great skill from any performer. If you pay attention to the "rez", i.e., the opening part of the "Lazgi" tune, you will discover the meaning in the actions of the dancer. If you watch the game, you can learn about natural phenomena from dance movements. For example, movements representing the earth, sky, sea waves, flying birds, water waves, and especially the sun are reflected in the Lazgi dance. The beginning of "Lazgi" has a strictly fixed character. No matter which type of "Lazgi" dance is performed, no matter which type of "Lazgi" is created, it expresses the creation of the world, existence, natural phenomena, and through dance movements, it seems to strictly adhere to the process of human resurrection. These methods have been proven both scientifically and mythically in the performance of dancers [1].

It is no exaggeration to say that all types of art have the power to create positive states in a person. Art is one of the spheres that direct people to health, to raise the spiritual world view, to purify the spiritual world, to good deeds. For example, in the art of dance, dancers who create a certain image live in this process without expressing their feelings, thoughts and experiences through the image. The audience perceives and feels these situations and enjoys the aesthetic beauty, and also receives psychological, spiritual and cultural nourishment.

The art of dancing has great potential for physical development. Two thousand years ago, the ancient Greek philosopher Plato wrote: "Dances are designed to shape the body." As a result of technical progress, many conveniences and conditions have been created for people, as a result of which people are less active, which certainly does not affect their health.

Health is a balanced unity of biological, mental, spiritual, physical conditions and labor activity of the human organism [2].

Every country has its own dance art, and this dance is a reflection of the people. Since ancient times, musicologists, thinkers and scientists have

confirmed the great potential of the art of dance to influence the human psyche, and its great importance in creating an educational and healthy lifestyle.

"Lazgi" dance awakens the spirit, raises the mood, has a positive effect on the nervous system of the child. Unknowingly, the child begins to move, increases the psycho-emotional mood of the child. Musical dance "Lazgi" has great health and educational value. Positive emotions cause a desire to perform actions more energetically, which increases their effect on the body, increases work performance, and also helps to improve health, study and active recreation.

There are legends that Abu Ali Ibn Sina used various methods of treatment (treatment with herbs, spiritual influence) for his sick patients. In fact, these are facts that have become myths.

Ibn Sina said that the origin of diseases depends on the nervous system, that anger, fear, strong compression weakens the body and affects it. He proved this opinion through experience. Ibn Sina kept one sheep in normal conditions and the other one in a cage and fed them both equally. A wolf was walking around a sheep in a cage. After a couple of days, a sheep in a cage with a wolf around it stops eating and dies of exhaustion. Ibn Sina concluded that the reason for the sheep's death was mental stress and, as a result, exhaustion of the body [3].

Dance-Movement Therapy (DMT) is a form of psychotherapy that uses dance and movement as a process to promote emotional and physical integration of the individual.

The transition of dance to a therapeutic style is often associated with the movements of the American dance teacher and dancer Marion Chase. She noticed a personal change in the students in her classes who were more interested in the expression of emotion in dance than in the dance technique itself. Chase later turned more to freedom of movement, discovering the psychological benefits dance offered. Initially, she worked with children and adolescents in her studio and in special schools. His work then impressed psychologists and psychiatrists, who began referring patients to him[5].

So, based on the above, we can say that the art of dance is one of the art forms that reflect the history, national traditions, values, and attractive actions of our people. The art of national dance forms a person into a physically, mentally and spiritually perfect person.

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